

3D-ERFASSUNG UND FAIRE PUBLIKATION VON CULTURAL HERITAGE ARTEFAKTEN

*AM BEISPIEL VON OGHAM STEINEN, HOLY WELLS UND WEITEREN
ARTEFAKTEN IN ZUSAMMENARBEIT MIT CITIZEN SCIENTISTS*

FLORIAN THIERY /w A.-K. DISTEL & N. WHITE & M. KASTEN

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BY

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ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

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NACHHALTIGE, NACHVOLLZIEHBARE, KOLLABORATIVE (3D-)ERFASSUNG UND
FAIRIFIZIERUNG WIRD IN DER CITIZEN SCIENCE COMMUNITY IMMER WICHTIGER.

NUR SO KÖNNEN DIESE DATEN MIT ANDEREN DATEN VERNETZT
UND IN INTERNATIONALE INITIATIVEN ...

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DIESE KÖNNEN VON INITIATIVEN WIE Z.B.
DEM RESEARCH SQUIRREL ENGINEERS NETWORK GENUTZT WERDEN ...

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... UM SO TEIL EINES ARCHÄOLOGISCHEN WISSENS-GRAPHEN ZU WERDEN
UND DEN BEREITS BESTEHENDEN DURCH QUALIFIZIERTE DATEN ANZUREICHERN.

ZUR ERFASSUNG UND BEREITSTELLUNG VON MEDIEN
GIBT ES Z.B. WIKIMEDIA COMMONS.

KIRI Engine

AUCH DIE DIGITALE LOW-COST ERFASSUNG MIT STRUCTURE FROM MOTION (SFM) TECHNOLOGIEN IST MIT DEM SMARTPHONE AUCH FÜR NICHT GEODÄTEN MÖGLICH.

VOR MEHR ALS 10 JAHREN GAB ES NOCH 123DCATCH...

GIPSEFIGUR UND SFM MIT 123DCATCH

3D-Modell berechnet mit KIRI engine
Vertices: 241'363 | Faces 482'116

Vertices x 5 !

3D-Modell berechnet mit 123Dcatch
Vertices: 46'097 | Faces 92'205

VERGLEICH NACH CA. 10 JAHREN MIT AI-UNTERSTÜTZUNG

DAS TEILEN DER DATEN KANN ÜBER OPEN SOURCE 3DHOP-INSTANZEN
INKL. LINKED DATA DOKUMENTATION ERFOLGEN.

DIE (SEMANTISCHE) BEREITSTELLUNG VON IST AUCH FÜR DIE
CITIZEN SCIENCE COMMUNITY OFFENEN PLATTFORMEN MÖGLICH.

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STRUCTURE FROM MOTION

Image via van Riel (2016) 10.13140/RG.2.1.4738.2643

DAS PRINZIP HINTER STRUCTURE FROM MOTION (SfM)

Image Bianco (2018) via 10.3390/jimaging4080098

Image Joshi (2022):

<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/structure-from-motion-manish-joshi/>

DAS PRINZIP HINTER STRUCTURE FROM MOTION (SfM)

OSM FOR HISTORY BUFFS

exploring irish history

Anne-Karoline Distel

@OSM4HistoryBuffs · 872 Abonnenten · 244 Videos

Das Hauptaugenmerk dieses Kanals sind Tutorials zum Kartografieren!

facebook.com/OSMForHistoryBuffs

Abonniert

<https://www.youtube.com/@OSM4HistoryBuffs/videos>

https://youtu.be/4SewzmdxsVo?si=RyX3t_DDzyVTuxDw

<https://youtu.be/D5I3Ck2ksTc?si=We71NuAltaRAYgRi>

Validation process in the Task Manager for osm:RL buildings
93 Aufrufe · vor 9 Monaten

Exploring and mapping pavement lights
605 Aufrufe · vor 9 Monaten

KiriEngine: Tipps und Tricks
74 Aufrufe · vor 9 Monaten

Creating Photogrammetry Models and Uploading them to Sketchfab
461 Aufrufe · vor 10 Monaten

Sketchfab-Links zu OpenStreetMap hinzufügen
72 Aufrufe · vor 10 Monaten

Stiefelabstreifanten kartografieren
203 Aufrufe · vor 10 Monaten

KIRI TUTORIALS MIT ANNE-KAROLINE

KIRI Engine

BEISPIEL MILESTONE MAUDLIN STREET

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oM6T7>

A.-K. D., CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/8912202795>

Knoten: 8912202795 ✕

Version #5

changed url:sketchfab to short link

Bearbeitet vor 11 Monaten von b-unicycling

Änderungssatz #143013535

Standort: 52.6525592, -7.2442662

Tags

historic	milestone
inscription	57
url:sketchfab	https://skfb.ly/oM6T7
wikimedia_commons	File:Maudlin_St_milest one.png

MILESTONE MAUDLIN STREET (KILKENNY) IN SKETCHFAB & OSM

Louise Rokohl, Florian Thiery, Anke Dingler, & Samantha Beck. (2021). African Red Slip Ware Digital (ARS3D) - How to create a Feature?. In Squirrel Papers, 3(1), #4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642977>

Thiery, Florian, Thiery Homburg, Anne-Karoline Distel, and Peter Thiery. 2024. '3D und FDM: Beispiele Für Semantische 3D-Annotation Und -Modellierung Im Datenqualifizierungsprozess in Konsortium Der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI)'. In Photogrammetrie – Laserscanning – Optische 3D-Messtechnik. Beiträge Der Oldenburger 3D-Tage und des BIMtages 2024., edited by Thomas Luhmann and Till Sieberth, 84–93. Berlin: Wichmann Verlag.

WAS KANN MAN DAMIT MACHEN? BEISPIEL: ANNOTATION

GRUNDLAGEN

LINKED DATA & WIKIDATA

FÜR DIE VERKNÜPFUNG VON DATEN UND DIE FAIRIFIZIERUNG IST
LINKED OPEN DATA (LOD) DIE METHODE DER WAHL.

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Practices of Linked Open Data in Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata

 by Sophie C. Schmidt ^{1,*}
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(This article belongs to the Special Issue Bridging Digital Approaches and Legacy in Archaeology)

Abstract

In this paper, we introduce Linked Open Data (LOD) in the archaeological domain as a means to connect dispersed data sources and enable cross-querying. The technology behind the design principles and how LOD can be created and published is described to enable less-familiar researchers to understand the presented benefits and drawbacks of LOD. Wikidata is introduced as an open knowledge hub for the creation and dissemination of LOD. Different actors within archaeology have implemented LOD, and we present which challenges have been and are being addressed. A selection of projects showcases how Wikidata is being used by archaeologists to enrich and open their databases to the general public. With this paper, we aim to encourage the creation and re-use of LOD in archaeology, as we believe it offers an improvement on current data publishing practices.

Keywords: linked open data; Wikidata; archaeology

Altmetric

Share

Help

Cite

Discuss in SciProfiles

Endorse

Comment

LINKED DATA UND WIKIDATA IN DER ARCHÄOLOGIE → MAL LESEN :-)

Olaf Tausch, CC BY 3.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Grafiken: Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via 10.3390/digital2030019

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q465338>

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q249707>

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/P189>

LINKED DATA IN WIKIDATA AM BEISPIEL DES DISKOS VON PHAISTOS

LINKED DATA IN WIKIDATA AM BEISPIEL DES DISKOS VON PHAISTOS

WIKIDATA-DATENMODELL AM BEISPIEL DES DISKOS VON PHAISTOS

Cradle tool

prähistorische keramik

Labels * SBK-Scherbe Hohenbrück

Alias Text

Beschreibungen Scherbe, evtl eines Tiergefäßes aus Hohenbrück

Ist ein(e) Wandscherbe

Material *

Bild

hat dekoratives Muster Stempel

Kultur

Entdecker oder Erfinder

Fundort

Zeitpunkt der Entdeckung oder Erfindung

- Einschnitt
- Stempel
- Kerbe
- Dreieck
- Linie
- Punkt
- Viereck**
- Kreis
- Streifen
- Wellenform
- Fingerkniff
- Wulst
- Knubbe

Property	Data Entry Options	Example: Q111600125
instance of (P31)	mandatory: archaeological find (Q10855061) and pottery ware (Q17379525)	archaeological find (Q10855061) and pottery ware (Q17379525)
made from material (P186)	mandatory: ceramic (Q45621)	ceramic (Q45621)
instance of (P31)	drop-down-menu: rim sherd (Q106990428), wall sherd (Q106990472), base sherd (Q106990489), ...	wall sherd (Q106990472)
image (P18)	free field to link to Wikimedia file	SBK-Scherbe_Hohenbrück.jpg
has pattern (P5422)	drop-down-menu: incising (Q6014696), stamp (Q96093273), triangle (Q19821), line (Q1228250), quadrilateral (Q36810), ...	stamp (Q96093273) and quadrilateral (Q36810)
culture associated with item (P2596)	drop-down-menu: Linear Pottery Culture (Q806348), Stroke-ornamented Ware Culture (Q1932196), Rössen Culture (Q1886212), ...	Stroke-ornamented Ware Culture (Q1932196)
discoverer or inventor (P61)	free field to link to Wikidata item	
location of item at discovery (P189)	free field to link to Wikidata item	Hohenbrück (Q1623655)
time of discovery (P575)	free field to enter date	
part of WikiProject (P5008)	mandatory: Prehistoric Ceramics (Q107588426)	Prehistoric Ceramics (Q107588426)
stated in (P248)	drop-down-menu: volunteer (Q24716636), Heritage Management of Baden-Württemberg (Q1541782), Heritage Management of Bavaria (Q812412), ... all other German Heritage Management institutions	Heritage Management of Brandenburg (Q897952)
described by source (P1343)	free field to link to Wikidata item	
described by URL (P973)	free field to enter URL	https://brandenburgikon.net/index.php/de/sachlexikon/stichbandkeramik

Grafiken: Sophie C. Schmidt, CC BY 4.0, via 10.3390/digital2030019

WIKIDATA UND CITIZEN SCIENCE: SMASHED DISHES

Wikidata Query Service Beispiele Hilfe Weitere Werkzeuge Abfragegenerator

Abfragehelfer

Filter

- Kultur Stichbandkeramik
- ist ein(e) Töpferware

Anzeigen

- Fundort
- Bild
- Fundort
- geographische Koordinaten

Begrenzung

```

1 #select ceramic finds Stichband culture: https://w.wiki/6EJz
2 SELECT ?SBK_KulturLabel ?Fundort ?FundortLabel ?Bild ?geographischeKoordinaten (GROUP_CONCAT(DISTINCT ?istLabel; SEPAR
3 SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
4 ?SBK_Kultur wdt:P2596 wd:Q1932196;
5 wdt:P31 wd:Q17379525.
6 OPTIONAL { ?SBK_Kultur wdt:P189 ?Fundort. }
7 OPTIONAL {
8 ?SBK_Kultur wdt:P31 ?ist.
9 ?ist rdfs:label ?istLabel.
10 FILTER((LANG(?istLabel)) = "de")
11 }
12 OPTIONAL { ?SBK_Kultur wdt:P18 ?Bild. }
13 OPTIONAL {
14 ?SBK_Kultur wdt:P189 ?Fundort.
15 ?Fundort wdt:P625 ?geographischeKoordinaten.
16 }
17 }
18 GROUP BY ?SBK_KulturLabel ?Fundort ?FundortLabel ?Bild ?geographischeKoordinaten
19

```

23 Ergebnisse in 466 ms

BEISPIELE AUS SMASHED DISHES – ARCHAEOLOGICAL SOURCES IN WIKIDATA

BEISPIELE AUS SMASHED DISHES – ARCHAEOLOGICAL SOURCES IN WIKIDATA

GRUNDLAGEN

OPEN STREET MAP

OPEN STREET MAP - HOW TO DO?

OpenStreetMap: an opportunity for Citizen Science

Alessandro Sarretta^{1,2}, Marco Minghini³, Maurizio Napolitano⁴, Alexander Kotsev⁵, Peter Mooney²
 1 CNR-IRPI, 2 Wikimedia Italia, 3 European Commission - Joint Research Centre, 4 Fondazione Bruno Kessler, 5 Maynooth University

OpenStreetMap (OSM, <https://www.openstreetmap.org>) is currently the largest, richest, most up-to-date and complete open geospatial database, in the world. OSM is probably the most popular crowdsourced geographic information project in the world.

OSM and science

There are various research topics related to OSM, mainly focused on:

- use of the data for scientific, domain-specific purposes
- analysis of contribution patterns
- engagement with the community (CS)
- assessing the quality of the data in OSM

What you can find (and contribute) to OSM

Thousands of [map features](#) with a simple data model and a flexible and extensible tagging system, e.g.:

- Land use
- Natural phenomena (rivers, lakes, forests, valleys, ...)
- Buildings and road networks
- Points of interest (hospitals, hotels, ...)

Main OSM pros

- Worldwide project
- Community-driven
- Multilingual community
- Local knowledge applied to global goals
- Open data ([ODbL licence](#))
- Open ecosystem of tools and services
- Feature-rich and detailed data model supporting micromapping

How OSM and Citizen Science can help each other

OSM can contribute to CS in different ways:

- tools and services for collection and extraction of geospatial information,
- background maps in different flavours,
- data and products open licensing,
- sustainability and preservation of Citizen Science data,
- project governance,
- community engagement

Citizen Science can contribute to OSM with:

- valuable, verified data that will improve an open data ecosystem ensuring accessibility and reusability by everyone,
- attract/involve new people in the contribution to OSM,
- extend OSM both geographically and thematically,
- custom tools serving specific CS needs that might be integrated in the OSM technical ecosystem

Useful OSM links: [mailing lists](#), [wiki](#), [Telegram groups](#), [Learn OSM](#), [weeklvosm.eu](#)

This poster is available under a [CC-BY 4.0 license](#).

Please cite it as: Sarretta A., Minghini M., Napolitano M., Kotsev A., Mooney P. (2020) OpenStreetMap: an opportunity for Citizen Science. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3992341>

OPEN STREET MAP UND CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJEKTE

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DE Diskussion

DE:Stolpersteine

Deutsch English français

Stolpersteine – Weitere Sprachen

Andere Sprachen...

In manchen Straßen finden sich im Bereich der Gehwege Plattensteine mit den Inschriften von Opfern des 3. Reiches. Diese Steine stammen aus dem Projekt Stolpersteine^[?] des Künstlers Gunter Demnig^[?]. Stolpersteine bestehen aus einer Messingplatte (mit der Inschrift), die fest mit einem darunter liegenden Betonklotz verbunden ist – nach der Verlegung ist für einen Betrachter nur die Messingplatte sichtbar. Die Erfassung dieser Steine eignet sich insbesondere auch für Schulprojekte, um mehr über die Vergangenheit der eigenen Stadt zu erfahren.

Die OSM-Community in Essen^[1]^[?] hat sich 2010 sehr intensiv mit dem Thema auseinandergesetzt.

Stolpersteine liegen meist vor der letzten frei gewählten Wohnstätte eines (oder mehrerer) von den Nazis deportierten und i. d. R. auch ermordeten Menschen (Juden, politisch Verfolgte, Homosexuelle etc.). Es gibt auch Stolpersteine, die vor der Arbeitsstätte^[2]^[?], der Schule^[3]^[?] oder anderen Orten, die im Zusammenhang mit der betroffenen Person stehen^[4]^[?], liegen. Es ist immer der Name des Opfers bekannt, sowie oftmals weitere Daten wie Geburtsdatum, Sterbedatum, Todesursache, Ort des Todes etc.^[5]^[?].

Stand Mai 2023 wurden in mindestens 27 verschiedenen Ländern bereits über 100.000 Stolpersteine verlegt. Die Stolpersteine gehen als die größte dezentrale Mahnmahl der Welt.

In OSM erfasste Steine je nach benutzten Tags (da ein „Doppeltagging“ möglich ist, lässt sich eine Gesamtanzahl daraus nicht direkt ableiten):

monorail:stolpersteine	monorail:typ:stolpersteine	monorail:stolpersteine	monorail:typ:stolpersteine
35 35 998	Attribut kommt in der OSM-Datenbank nicht vor.	35 35	Attribut kommt in der OSM-Datenbank nicht vor.
hier auftragen	hier auftragen	hier auftragen	hier auftragen

i Eine Übersicht mit verlegten und bereits in OSM eingetragenen Stolpersteinen sowie weitere aktuelle Informationen befinden sich im Artikel [DE:Städte mit Stolpersteinen](#).

Inhaltsverzeichnis [Verbergen]

- 1 Tagging
- 1.1 Wie mappen?
- 2 Karten
- 3 Soll-Ist-Abgleich-Tool
- 4 Statistik
- 5 Links

via <https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/DE:Stolpersteine>

PROJEKT: STOLPERSTEINE

Evaluating linked data location based services using the example of Stolpersteine

Timo Homburg*, Klaus Böhm*, Nicole Bruhn*, Gregor Hubrich*

*Mainz, University Of Applied Sciences, Germany, {timo.homburg,klaus.boehm,nicole.bruhn}@hs-mainz.de

*Corresponding Author

Abstract: In this publication we introduce a linked data powered application which assists users to find so-called Stolpersteine, stones commemorating Jewish victims of the second world war. We show the feasibility of a dedicated location based service as an app using linked data resources and evaluate this approach against local data sources gathered by communities to find out if the current linked data environment can equally or sufficiently support an application in this knowledge domain.

Keywords: Stolperstein, linked data, app, location based service

CC BY 4.0 via <https://13mainz.github.io/stolperstein/>

1. Introduction

A common problem for the geospatial community is the evaluation of data sources in terms of fitness for use (Picas et al., 2014), i.e. if the quality of the data sources is sufficient enough to support a certain use case. Data quality is commonly measured using data quality metrics customized for a specific use case (Homburg and Bochs, 2019) to quantify the fitness for use of the respective data set. We would like to test the fitness for use of (linked) open data sources representing Stolpersteine (Franke and Deming, 2009), stones commemorating Jewish victims of the second world war in three similar-sized cities of Germany. We compare (linked) open data sources against our gold standard data. Data sources which have been collected by local communities or historical societies (official data) dedicated to preserving the history of the city in which they operate. For our success in this publication, we traced those back to Wikipedia lists for which we are sure the local communities maintain them. As we will describe in more detail in Section 2.3, many of the local communities provide means of accessing Stolperstein data such as maps or apps linked to their respective area of operation. The research question proposed in our publication is to which extent (linked) open data sources can provide an equivalent fitness for use for the use case of an interested source/interested person compared to the data provided by the local community. The results of this analysis case provide indicators of the use fitness for a variety of possible linked data powered applications such as city tour planning apps, geofencing apps or apps advising communities about possible maintenance work (e.g. polishing) of Stolpersteine and the methodology itself is useful to validate a variety of similar location based services in terms of their fitness for use. The paper is structured as follows: In Section 2 we discuss related work concerning geospatial linked open data, geospatial data quality assessment and existing Stolperstein applications. In Section 3 we explain how we gather (linked) open data resources for our comparison case which we describe in Section 4. The results of our experiment are presented in Section 5 and discussed in Section 6 before we conclude the paper in Section 7.

MIT DER APP „STONEVIEWER“ AUF DER SPUR DER MAINZER STOLPERSTEINE

Projektleitung

Prof. Dr. Klaus Böhm
(Fachbereich Technik / 13mainz -
Institut für Raumbezogene
Informations- und Messtechnik)

Projektleiterarbeit

Gregor Hubrich
Timo Homburg M. Sc.
Nicole Bruhn M.A.

Laufzeit

Februar bis September 2019

Finanzierung

aus eigenen Mitteln finanziert

Kontakt

13mainz@hs-mainz.de

Die App StoneViewer

Wie sich den in Mainz verlegten Stolpersteinen sucht, kann nun mit seinem Smartphone auf die App „StoneViewer“ zur Visualisierung raumbezogener Daten zurückgreifen, die Gregor Hubrich im Rahmen seiner Bachelorarbeit in der Fachrichtung Geoinformatik und Vermessung der Hochschule Mainz erstellt hat.

Diese unterscheidet sich von den bereits existierenden mobilen Anwendungen im Wesentlichen durch zwei Aspekte: Zum einen stützt sich Hubrich auf die PWA-Methode: Progressive Web Apps sind Anwendungen, die im Webbrowser laufen. Diese innovativen Webanwendungen ermöglichen unter anderem das Arbeiten im

Offline-Betrieb und auch die Verwendung von Push-Benachrichtigungen.

Die zweite Besonderheit liegt darin, dass die raumbezogenen Angaben zu den Stolpersteinen über die Einblendung offener Daten erfolgen: Der „StoneViewer“ greift auf die Webquellen Wikidata und OpenStreetMap (OSM) zu. Auch Funktionen wie das Anzeigen und Verfolgen der eigenen Position oder das Geofencing können realisiert werden. Letzteres bedeutet, dass das Smartphone die Position von Stolpersteinen in der Umgebung des Nutzers ermittelt, anzeigt und diesen über eine Push-Benachrichtigung informiert. Dieser Mechanismus lässt sich in den Einstellungen des StoneViews konfigurieren.

Karte in GitHub, die angibt, zu welchem Ort die Mainzer Stolpersteine schon in OSM und Wikidata eingepflegt sind. (<https://13mainz.github.io/stolperstein/#>)

Gregor Hubrich erklärt seinem Gast den StoneViewer
Foto: 13mainz, CC-BY-SA 4.0

So können die Optionen „Geolocator“ und „Benachrichtigungen“ ein- oder ausgeschaltet werden. In einem Schieberegler kann außerdem eine Distanz zwischen 0 und 500 Metern gewählt werden. Liegt die Entfernung zu einem Stolperstein unterhalb der an diesem Regler eingestellten Grenze, wird eine Benachrichtigung ausgeben.

Anlässlich des Mainzer Wissenschaftsmarktes, der Mitte September 2019 stattfand, wurde der „StoneViewer“ erstmals öffentlich vorgestellt. Besucherinnen und Besucher konnten mit Hilfe der App die Stolpersteine in der Umgebung des Gutenbergplatzes aufsuchen. Die meisten Nutzer fanden den Umgang mit der App sehr intuitiv. Manche Nutzer wünschten sich zur besseren Orientierung eine Richtungsangabe. Diese und weitere Verbesserungen sind für die nächste Version geplant. Die auf dem Stand des 13mainz Anwesenden nutzten die zwei Tage des Wissenschaftsmarktes, um die Mainzer Stolpersteine, die noch nicht in OpenStreetMap und Wikidata eingetragen waren, nachzutragen, sodass nun alle derzeit 228 Mainzer Stolpersteine in der App angezeigt werden.

Linked Open Data versus Open Data

In einer wissenschaftlichen Veröffentlichung für die International Cartographic Association (Publikation in „Advances in Cartography and GIScience of the ICA“ in Vorbereitung) zeigten Timo Homburg, Klaus Böhm, Nicole Bruhn und Gregor Hubrich, dass eine App, deren Daten aus offenen Datenquellen stammen, zuverlässige Resultate liefern kann. Unterstützt werden die Linked-Open-Data-Quellen aus Wikidata und Open Street Map

zu Wiesbaden, Mainz und Achafenburg am Beispiel der Stolpersteine. Als Vergleich dienten Daten, die von lokales Geoinformations gesammelt und im Internet zur Verfügung gestellt wurden waren. Die Autoren sehen in der Methode großes Potenzial, lässt sie sich doch weltweit und auf unterschiedliche Gattungen bezogen anwenden. Allerdings bleibt das angezeigte Resultat stets abhängig von der Anzahl der in die offenen Datenquellen eingesperrten Daten.

Ausblick

Die Weiterentwicklung kann in unterschiedliche Richtungen erfolgen. Zum einen können die Stolperstein-App sowie die Serverkomponenten erweitert werden. Hilfreich wäre eine Überprüfung der Daten zugrundeliegenden Koordinaten unter Verwendung professioneller GPS-Vermessungssysteme. Vorstellbar ist auch die Verknüpfung mit weiteren semantischen Daten, um das Leben der betroffenen Person, ihren Herkunft, verwandtschaftliche Bezüge, Beruf etc. bereit zu stellen. Funktionen wie das Clustering von Familien, bei dem Ähnlichkeitsstrukturen in großen Datenbeständen ermittelt werden, oder die Darstellung historischer Ereignisse könnten verwirklicht werden. Zur Weiterentwicklung der „StoneViewer“-App könnten außerdem zusätzliche Funktionen zur Interaktion mit dem mobilen Geotextsystem implementiert werden. Zum anderen ist geplant, die entwickelten Technologien an neue Anwendungsfelder anzupassen.

Die wissenschaftliche Leitung hat nun Prof. Dr. Pascal Neis übernommen.

Der QR-Code führt zur
Webseite des StoneViewers:
<https://13mainz.github.io/stolperstein/>

Mit dem StoneViewer können Stolpersteine in bis zu 500 Metern Entfernung ausfindig gemacht werden. Foto: 13mainz, CC-BY-SA 4.0

PROJEKT: STOLPERSTEINE AM 13 MAINZ

REAL WORLD USE CASES

OGHAM!

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.502

4.-6. JHD.N.CHR.
EARLY MEDIEVAL
“PRIMITIVE IRISH”

VERBREITUNG
IRLAND
(+ WALES, ENGLAND, ISLE OF MAN)

Al-qamar / CC BY-SA 3.0 via
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REAL WORLD USE CASES

OGHAM IN 3D / OG(H)AM PROJEKT

NORA WHITE & MEGAN KASTEN @ CORK

Ogham in 3D+

Digitisation, digital epigraphy and cross-sector collaboration in the study of ogham

Nora White · Early Irish MU

DIAS

Institiúid Ard-Léinn | Dublin Institute for
Bhaile Átha Cliath | Advanced Studies

The Discovery Programme

Centre for Archaeology
and Innovation Ireland

OGHAM IN 3D

An Roinn Cultúir,
Oidhreacht agus Gaeltachta
Department of Culture,
Heritage and the Gaeltacht

museum

National Museum of Ireland
Ard-Mhúsaem na hÉireann

<https://ogham.celt.dias.ie>

DAS OGHAM IN 3D PROJEKT SCANNT OGHAM STEINE IN IRLAND ...

Encoded in XML
Following EpiDoc guidelines
Subset of Text Encoding Initiative


```

<asc>
<ortDesc>
<support>
<p>National Monuments Service Record Number: <ref target="https://maps.archaeology.ie/HistoricEnvir
<material ref="materials.xml#stone">Stone</material> <objectType ref="objects.xml#mon1">pillar<
described by <ref source="#MAC1945">Macalister (1945, 3)</ref> as <q>q-grit</q>
(<dimensions unit="m" source="https://maps.archaeology.ie/HistoricEnvironment/?SHRS=MA093-0380
<height>1.80</height>
<width>0.60</width>
<depth>0.35</depth>
</dimensions>). The stone<q> has a rectangular cross-section, straight sides which taper at th
<portDesc>
<outDesc>
<layout>As the stone is currently leaning to an almost horizontal position, <q>the ogham inscription is
the stone, formerly the E face when the stone was vertical</q> (<ref source="https://maps.archaeology
The inscription is <rs type="execution" key="pocked" ref="https://www.eagle-network.eu/voc/writing/lo
AVI (except the distal ends of the V) and parts of some other scores are chipped away; a flake about
broken off. The space available does not confirm Rhys's contention that the second word should be AVE
<outDesc>
<desc>
Diplomatic: +n +llllllllll +llllllllll +llllllllll
Interpretive: ALATTOS MAQI BR[ ... ]
<div type="edition" xml:space="preserve" xml:lang="ggl" resp="#NW">
<ab>
<lb nr="1" style="text-direction:up"/>
<persName><name nymRef="#ALLATUS" corresp="http://www.dil.ie/2930">AL<unclear reason="
<w lemma="MAQAS" type="patronym" corresp="http://www.dil.ie/31166">MAQI</w>
<persName><name>BR<gap reason="lost" extnt="unknown"/></name></persName>
</div>
</ab>

```


<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ma073-012-kilmovee-371f70c582cb45c295bec7263c41bc38>

... BEI NUTZUNG VON SFM UND SLPS UND DOKUMENTATION MIT TEI EPIDOC ...

slides by Nora White

*this is a list of recorded sites thus far. Please click on an image to go to that site.

<http://www.corcadhuibhne3d.ie> <https://skfb.ly/6LR7Y>

Ballymoreeagh

Killofman

Rathclubb

Ballinabit

Reask D

Correuly

Virtual Heritage in Schools pilot programme

... UND TRANSDISZIPLINÄREN AUSTAUSCH.

slides by Megan Kasten

OG(H)AM
Increasing digital footprints
to research and teaching practices
writing from the 18th century to the 21st

University of Glasgow

Maynooth University
National University of Ireland Maynooth

IRISH RESEARCH COUNCIL
An Chomhairle um Thailghe in Éirinn

Arts & Humanities Research Council

OG(H)AM in 3D

Dr Megan Kasten
UK Postdoctoral Researcher OG(H)AM

DH UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association
UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association, 4-5 June 2024 University College Cork

Photogrammetry

- Data capture mostly in museums or in remote locations
 - Limited opportunities for photogrammetry workshops
- Gigha, with Isle of Gigha Heritage Trust
- More recently, 3D printing
 - Easier to demonstrate

Photos by Katherine Forsyth

OG(H)AM IN 3D ARBEITET MIT DEN GLEICHEN METHODEN ...

slides by Megan Kasten

3D – Keeping the data FAIR

- Primarily photogrammetry, and RTI where needed, with some structured light scanning
- Archive will be at University of Glasgow: Enlighten, and National Monuments Record Digital Archives (HES, RCAHMW), Digital Repository of Ireland
 - DNG
 - Processed Jpegs and Masks
 - Agisoft Metashape files, processing reports, camera positions (XML)
 - OBJ and textures
 - PLY (3DHop requirement)

Latheron (S-SUT-002) NMS

Metadata

- Embedded in images (DNG, jpeg)
- Context of data capture, where the artefact/stone was originally found
- CC Licensing info – needs to be better (pending museum legal teams..)

... UM DIE DATEN FAIR BEREITZUSTELLEN ...

slides by Megan Kasten

3D – Open (where possible) and Accessible

- Ogham in 3D currently uses Sketchfab to embed the 3D images on the website
- OG(H)AM - Moving away from Sketchfab
 - 3DHop
 - Open-source viewer for high resolution 3D
 - University of Oslo KHM - BitFROST
 - Most downloadable, like O3D
 - Partner museums – downloadable?
 - High resolution via 3DHop

3D – Challenges with Reusing data

- Processing Status
 - Funding wasn't always available for processing
 - Uni College Cork – around 20 ogham stones
 - Unprocessed Minolta VI-900 laser scans by Archaeoptics (Alistair Carty) – (2003, 2006)
 - Unprocessed Artec structured light scans by Discovery Programme for O3D (2012-2015)+
 - Artec – will processing old scans with new software improve resolution?
 - Reusable?
- How to avoid proprietary software issues in the future?

Image: <https://www.ucc.ie/en/discover/visit/stone-corridor/>

... UND ZU VERÖFFENTLICHEN; PROBLEME BEIM "R" BLEIBEN ...

Loss of relative spatial information between proprietary scans (2003)

slides by Megan Kasten

Artec – Processing Old Scans

- Processing and reprocessing

I-WAT-021 Fox's Castle; Data captured 2016, processed 2024

I-FER-002_Ballydoolough
Left: Processed 2017 on 'Fast Fusion'
Right: Processed 2024 on 'Sharp Fusion'

... JEDOCH UND MÜSSEN GELÖST WERDEN!

via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/152_Ballinrannig_V

```
▼ object {1}
  ▼ TEI {3}
    ▼ teiHeader {4}
      ▼ fileDesc {3}
        ▼ titleStm {3}
          title : CIIC 152. Ballinrannig V
        ▼ editor {3}
          persName : Nora White
          roleName : Principal Investigator
          orgName : Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies
        ▼ respStm {3}
          resp : captured by the Corca Dhuibhne 3d community project (Helena Zacharias) in 2017 using photogrammetry and processed by Discovery Programme using Agisoft Photoscan
          name : Gary Devlin
          orgName : Discovery Programme
      ▼ 7 {4}
        head : History of Recording
        ▼ p {3}
          ► h1 {2}
          ► ref {4}
            _text : First recognised in 1782 by Pelham and recorded by Vallancey (1804) in in 6, 226 in. This stone was recorded for the Ogham in 3D project in 2017 by Helena Zacharias, a participant on the Corca Dhuibhne 3d project, using Structure from Motion 3d technology.
            _type : history
            _n : record
```

CIIC 152. BALLINRANNIG V (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), CO. KERRY

via <https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/153>. Ballinrannig VI

```
▼ object {1}
  ▼ TEI {3}
    ▼ teiHeader {4}
      ▼ fileDesc {3}
        ▼ titleStmt {3}
          title : CIIC 153. Ballinrannig VI
        ► editor {3}
      ▼ respStmt {3}
        resp : captured by the Corca Dhuibhne 3d community project (Helena Zacharias) in 2017 using photogrammetry and processed by Discovery Programme using Agisoft Photoscan
        name : Gary Devlin
        orgName : Discovery Programme
        ▼ 7 {4}
          head : History of Recording
          ▼ p {3}
            ► hi {2}
            ► ref {4}
              _text : First recognised in 1782 by Pelham and recorded by Vallancey (1804) in \n 6, 226 \n. This stone was recorded for the Ogham in 3D project in 2017 by Helena Zacharias, a participant on the Corca Dhuibhne 3d project, using Structure from Motion 3d technology.
            _type : history
            n : record
```

CIIC 153. BALLINRANNIG VI (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), CO. KERRY

via <http://www.megalithicireland.com/Castletimon.htm>

via https://heritage.wicklowheritage.org/topics/events/castletimon_discoveries

oghamin3d, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oYpOo>


```
▼ object {1}
  ▼ TEI {3}
    ▼teiHeader {4}      via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/47\_Castletimon
      ▼ fileDesc {3}
        ▼ titleStm {3}
          title: CIIC 47. Castletimon
          ▼ editor {3}
            persName: Nora White
            roleName: Principal Investigator
            orgName: Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies
          ▼ respStm {3}
            resp: 3d model created using photogrammetry (68 images with a Canon EOS 1100D) on 6/8/2016 and processed using Agisoft PhotoScan software
            name: Nora White
```

CIIC 47. CASTLETIMON, CO. WICKLOW

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Replica!

The Discovery Programme, via <https://skfb.lv/VKFO>

via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/141_Aglish_I

Transliteration

MAQI MAQI/... OGGODIK[A]

Translation

... son of Mac...

Commentary

As noted by McManus (1991, 109) 'MAQ(Q)-X names can be distinguished from the patronymic MAQ(Q) X ['son of X] type either by appearing first on the inscription (e.g. 40 MAQI-CAIRATINI AVI INEQAGLAS) or [as in this case] by being preceded by MAQ(Q) ['son of'] or some other formula word.'

There is an example here of the use of the first supplementary character (or *forfid*). This character is used with two values: /ki/ or /xi/ (usually transliterated K, as here between two vowels) and vocalic value /ei/ (McManus 1991, 79).

```

object {1}
  ▼ TEI {3}
    ▼ teiHeader {4}
      ▼ fileDesc {3}
        ▼ titleStm {3}
          title : CIIC 141. Aglish
        ▼ editor {3}
          persName : Nora White
          roleName : Principal Investigator
          orgName : Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies
        ▼ respStm {3}
          resp : Scanned on 13/5/2016 using Artec Eva, structured-light scanner and
                processed using Geomagic software
          name : Rob Shaw
          orgName : The Discovery Programme

```

via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/141_Aglish_I

CIIC 141. AGLISH I (AN EAGLAIS), CO. KERRY

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Kerry3D @DH_Age, CC0, via <https://skfb.ly/ovOwS>

via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/142_Aglish_II

Transliteration

... CE|L|I AV|I V|U|D?

Translation

'... follower of the descendant of F?...'

Commentary

All that survives of this inscription are the possible remains of two formula words (CELLI 'companion, follower' and AVI 'grandson, descendant'), followed by the beginning of a personal name. This unusual combination of formula words is also found in an ogham inscription on a stone from Dromlohan, Co. Waterford (CIIC. 275).


```

object {1}
  TEI {3}
    teiHeader {4}
      fileDesc {3}
        titleStm {3}
          title : CIIC 142. Aglish
        editor {3}
          persName : Nora White
          roleName : Principal Investigator
          orgName : Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies
        respStm {3}
          resp : Scanned on 19/7/2013 using Artec Eva, structured-light scanner and
            processed using Geomagic software
          name : Rob Shaw
          orgName : The Discovery Programme
  
```

CIIC 142. AGLISH II (AN EAGLAIS), CO. KERRY

REAL WORLD USE CASES

OGHAM-FUND VON GRAHAM SENIOR IN COVENTRY (ENGLAND)

via <https://www.theguardian.com/science/article/2024/may/08/teacher-finds-stone-ancient-ogham-writing-ireland-coventry-garden>

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Archaeology

Teacher finds stone with ancient ogham writing from Ireland in Coventry garden

Exclusive: Sandstone rock featuring language markings created 1,600 years ago to go on display at museum

Dalya Alberge
Wed 8 May 2024 13.02 CEST
Share

The ogham stone, 11cm long and weighing 139g, was found in an overgrown garden. Photograph: The Herbert Art Gallery and Museum

A geography teacher was tidying his overgrown garden at his home in Coventry when he stumbled across a rock with mysterious incisions. Intrigued, he sent photographs to a local archaeologist and was taken aback to learn that the markings were created more than 1,600 years ago and that the artefact was worthy of a museum.

The rectangular sandstone rock that Graham Senior had discovered was inscribed in ogham, an alphabet used in the early medieval period primarily for writing in the Irish language.

Most viewed

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- Israeli soldiers and police tipping off groups that attack Gaza aid trucks
- Live Euro 2024: Rashford and Henderson out of Southgate's provisional England squad - live
- Microplastics found in every human testicle in study

CITIZEN SCIENTIST "GRAHAM SENIOR" HAT EINEN OGHAM STEIN GEFUNDEN ...

via <https://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/1004478>

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- [Statistics](#)

ESS-634434 - Roman coin

[View record](#) [Embed record](#) [Print](#)

INSCRIBED OBJECT

Unique ID: WMID-63443A

Object type certainty: Certain

Workflow status: Awaiting validation

A sub-rectangular, sandstone rock with ogham script inscribed down three of the four sides. The front and back sides are smooth. The rock is a dark grey colour and likely to be a thin type rock (metamorphic muscovite/slate). The inscriptions appear to have been done in a single action, not repeated.

It measures 110 ^{mm} in length, 36 ^{mm} wide and 19 ^{mm} thick, to weigh 139 g.

Katherine Forde (University of Glasgow) has confirmed that the markings are those of an ogham inscription. The script is that of an early style, most likely 5th to 6th Century but possibly as early as 4th Century. The script is similar to that on an ogham-inscribed knife handle from Wleaving, in Norfolk. The inscription reads: MALDUMCAL/S/LASS. The first part of the inscription relates to a person's name: Mael Dumcail. The second part is less certain.

Chemical composition of the stone surface is: Al 0.17%; Ca 2.65%; Hg 0.21%; P 0.27%; Pd 2.11%; Rh 2.56%; Cd 4.11%; Sn 8.43%; S 11.80%; Fe 67.68%

Find of note status

This is a find of note and has been designated: Regional importance

Inscription: MALDUMCAL/S/LASS

Subsequent actions

Current location of find: The Herbert Museum, Coventry

Subsequent action after recording: Donated to a museum

Chronology

Broad period: EARLY MEDIEVAL

Subsided from: Early

Period from: EARLY MEDIEVAL

Subsided to: Early

Period to: EARLY MEDIEVAL

Date from: Circa Δ 400

Date to: Circa Δ 500

Dimensions and weight

Quantity: 1

Length: 110 ^{mm}

Width: 36 ^{mm}

Thickness: 19 ^{mm}

Weight: 139 g

Discovery dates

Date(s) of discovery: Thursday 28th May 2020 - Thursday 28th May 2020

Personal details

This information is restricted for your access level.

Other reference numbers

Museum accession number: 2023.32.AR

Materials and construction

Primary material: Stone

Completeness: Complete

ESS-634434 - Roman coin

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... WELCHER IM PORTABLE ANTIQUITIES SCHEME VERFÜGBAR IST ...

Birmingham Museums Trust, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

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Birmingham Museums Trust, CC BY 4.0

... MIT BILDERN BESCHRIEBEN IST ...

... SOWIE ALS 3D MODELL ...

... ALS 3D-DRUCK ...

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/11890993295>

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export GPS-Tracks Benutzer-Blogs Gemeinschaften Urheberrecht Hilfe Über Anmelden Registrieren

Suchen Wo ist dies? Los +

Knoten: 11890993295

Version #4

added inscription to #ogham stone

Bearbeitet vor 12 Tagen von b-unicycling
Änderungssatz #151091812
Standort: 52.4073236, -1.5063250

Tags

covered	yes
fixme	move to exact location within the museum, if possible
height	0.11
historic	ogham_stone
inscription	𐌆𐌰𐌿𐌹𐌺𐌹𐌺𐌰𐌶𐌰𐌹𐌺𐌰𐌹𐌺𐌰𐌹𐌺𐌰𐌹𐌺𐌰
inscription:en	MALDUMCAIL / S / LASS
material	sandstone
moved	yes
moved_to:wikidata	Q917262
source:inscription:en	https://www.theguardian.com/science/article/2024/may/08/tea-cher-finds-stone-ancient-ogham-writing-ireland-coventry-garden

... IN OPEN STREET MAP ...

via <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q125855438>

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone from Coventry (Q125855438)

No description defined [edit](#)

WMID-83446A

[+ In more languages](#)

Compare

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone from Coventry	No description defined	WMID-83446A
German	Oghamstein aus Coventry	2009 antiker Oghamstein, jetzt in der Sammlung im Museum in Coventry	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of [ogham stone](#) [edit](#)

[+ 1 reference](#)

[Ogham Stone Concept](#) [edit](#)

[- 0 references](#) [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

image [edit](#)

WMID-83446A.jpg
10,480 × 5,720; 16.82 MB

[- 0 references](#) [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

collection [Herbert Art Gallery and Museum](#) [edit](#)

[- 0 references](#) [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

location of discovery [Coventry](#) [edit](#)

[+ 1 reference](#)

[Wikipedia](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

[Wikibooks](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

[Wikinews](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

[Wikiquote](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

[Wikisource](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

[Wikiversity](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

[Wikivoyage](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

[Wiktionary](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

[Multilingual sites](#) (0 entries) [edit](#)

... UND IN WIKIDATA!

The adjective máel (<https://dil.ie/31242>) 'crop-headed, shorn, tonsured' is a commonly found first element in early Irish (religious) personal names (examples here <https://dil.ie/31244>).

However, the second element **-dumeail** or **-dumcail** isn't clear. **Dumeail** is reminiscent of **DUMELEDONAS** (CIIC 368), **DUMELI** (CIIC 252), **DDUMILEAS** (CIIC 198) in ogham inscriptions, but the meaning is unknown and the element doesn't seem to be attested in later manuscript sources.

It's hard to say much about S and LASS but the sequence lass- is found in some later inscriptions, e.g. lassa·ndernad “for whom it has been made” (<https://emili.celt.dias.ie/LOU-001>).

There are also names that begin **lass-**, e.g. **Lassar** 'flame, fire' (<https://dil.ie/29600> or <https://www.dib.ie/biography/lassar-a4690>).

NICE TO KNOW

Birmingham Museums Trust, CC BY 4.0

Dumeledonas (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Rhys/1907, 80--81: 'The name Dumeledo, genitive Dumeledonas, claims kinship with Dumelus of the stone at Llanddewi-brefi...The meaning of the name Dumel-, eludes me; and I have to make the same confession as to the ending -edu or -edo'.

https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/stone/ldwke_1.html

Rhys, J. (1874):	--]MAQI[--] [--] TAQOLEDEMU[--] Expansion: [--]MAQI[--] TAQOLEDEMU Rhys/1874 19 reading only Westwood/1876 93 reading only
Rhys, J. (1906):	MAQI M[--] DUMELEDONAS Expansion: MAQI MUCOI DUMELEDONAS Translation: <i>Son of the kin of Dumeledonas (PN).</i> Macalister/1945 351 reading only Rhys/1877 398 reading only Rhys/1907 78--80 reading only Thomas/1994 98 reading only
Macalister, R.A.S. (1922):	--]MAQI M[--] TUMELEDONAS Expansion: --] MAQI MUCOI TUMELEDONAS Macalister/1922 22 reading only
Nash-Williams, V.E. (1950):	DUMELEDONAS MAQI M[--] Expansion: DUMELEDONAS MAQI MUCOI [--] Translation: <i>(The stone) of Dumeledo, son of the kin of...</i> Nash-Williams/1950 113 reading only

DUMELEDONAS (CIIC 368; CISP LDWKE/1)

Ogham in 3D, CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland,
via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/252_Gurran

https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/stone/guran_1.html

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): DUMELIMAQIGL ||| ASIC ||| ONAS | NIOTTACOBTRAN || OR[--]
Expansion:
 DUMELI MAQI GLASICONAS NIOTTA COBRANOR[IGAS]
[Macalister/1945](#) 247 reading only

McManus, D. (1991): DUMELIMAQIGL ||| ASIC ||| ONAS | NIOTTACOBTRAN || [O]R[--]
Expansion:
 DUMELI MAQI GLASICONAS NIOTTA COBRANOR[--]
[McManus/1991](#) 65 reading only

[Dumeli](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

[Glasiconas](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

See McManus 1991, 110, for discussion of the idea that GLASICONAS equated to c *glas*, an immigrant from outside Ireland.

McManus/1991, 102--105, 'GLASICONAS (*Glaistiuc*, gen. *Glaschor*) ... ('grey' + 'wolf').

[Cobranor\[igias\]](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Wikidata

252 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680996)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

in most languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	252 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of

- ogham stone [edit](#)
- 0 references [+ add reference](#)
- Ogham Stone Concept [edit](#)
- 0 references [+ add reference](#)
- Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project) [edit](#)

Wikipedia [edit](#)

Wikibooks [edit](#)

Wikinews [edit](#)

Wikiquote [edit](#)

Wikisource [edit](#)

Wikiversity [edit](#)

Wikivoyage [edit](#)

Wiktionary [edit](#)

Multilingual sites [edit](#)

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q106680996>

DUMELI (CIIC 252; CISP GURAN/1)

Ogham in 3D, CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland, via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/198_Coolmagort_I1

https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/stone/coolm_2.html

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): MAQIRITEASMAQIMAQIDDUMILEAS | MUCOITOICACI
Expansion:
 MAQI-RITEAS MAQI MAQI-DDUMILEAS MUCOI TOICACI
[Gippert Web 198](#) reading only [[Gippert 198](#)]
[Macalister 1945](#) 193 reading only
[McManus 1991](#) 65 reading only

[Maqi-Riteas](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
 McManus 1991, 109: 'MAQI-RITEAS ... (*Mac Rithe*)'.
[Maqi-Ddumileas](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
 McManus 1991, 109: 'MAQI-DDUMILEAS (gen. *Duimle*)'.
[Toicaci](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
 McManus 1991, 53: 'Three of the seven stones at Coolmagort, County Kerry [i.e. this stone and COOLM/1 and COOLM/4] ... Appear to commemorate members of the *toíath* of **Toicacas*'.

WIKIDATA

198 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680892)

Ogham Stone, Ireland edit

in more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	198 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	ogham stone edit	0 references add reference
	Ogham Stone Concept edit	0 references add reference
	Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project) edit	0 references add reference

Wikipedia edit

Wikibooks edit

Wikinews edit

Wikiquote edit

Wikisource edit

Wikiversity edit

Wikivoyage edit

Wiktionary edit

Multilingual sites edit

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q106680892>

Florian Thier / Peter Thier, CC BY 4.0

DUMELI (CIIC 198; CISP COOLM/2)

REAL WORLD USE CASES

OGHAM IN CORK

LINKED OPEN OGHAM ?!

I AM LOOKING FOR ALL OGHAM
STONES IN IRELAND...
WHERE CAN I FIND THEM?

Florian Thiery, CC BY-SA 4.0

LINKED OPEN OGHAM

ONLINE & OPEN:
3D OGHAM PROJECT

[HTTPS://OGHAM.CELTICDEAS.IE](https://ogham.celticdeas.ie)

HERITAGE MANAGEMENT

[HTTP://WERGIS.ARCHAEOLOGY.IE/HISTORY/ENVIRONMENT/](http://wergis.archaeology.ie/history/environment/)

ONLINE: CISP

[HTTPS://WWW.UCL.AC.UK/ARCHAEOLOGY/CISP/DATABASE/](https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/)

OFFLINE:

CIIC BY MACALISTER

THE OPEN OGHAM DATA WORKFLOW!

Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt und Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

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Wikidata:WikiProject Irish Ogham Stones

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Background [edit]

This is part of the funded Open Science Fallov Program, where I would like to create a semantically described, Linked Open Data^[1] (LOD) collection of Irish Ogham stones^[2] that is freely accessible to all in the spirit of Knowledge Equity. This collection is built on existing published research and can thus serve as another important research tool in the field of early medieval inscriptions.

On private journeys through Ireland, especially in the western part of the green isle, in the counties of Kerry and Cork, I have come across a mysterious script and stones as its original inscription carriers in various places. After initial research, these turned out to be Ogham stones with an early medieval Ogham script, one of Ireland's most remarkable national treasures. Ogham stones were placed in Ireland and the western part of Britain between the 4th and 9th century. The inscriptions carved on the stones show in particular kinship or tribal relationships and so may have served as gravestones or area demarcations. They are an important source for historians, but also for linguists and archaeologists. In order to bring this rich treasure of a small manageable corpus of inscriptions and stones as free knowledge to a large research community, the idea of the Ogham Project^[3] was born. This idea was initiated with friends in a spare time working group, the Research Squared Engineers^[4]. This has already resulted in the first modelling and publications of stones after Macalister in Wikidata^[5].

The semantic modelling will be done in two ways. On the one hand, the data (stones, sites, words, people, etc.) will be stored in Wikidata in order to integrate the data into the Linked Data Cloud and to offer the community the opportunity to participate in Free Knowledge in the field of Ogham inscriptions. This can be done, for example, by adding images of Ogham stones to Wikimedia Commons and by adding to and translating the explanatory Wikidata pages. On the other hand, the data will be stored in a separate Ogham ontology, made available via a SPARQL endpoint and linked to the stones available in Wikidata. This enables a deeper semantic modelling of the Ogham stones and their inscriptions and can thus contribute to an open and free scientific discourse. In addition, the Ogham stones will be made accessible on Wikidata and other Triplosites in a community-friendly web platform. Filter options for specific topics, such as words used, material or persons, as well as for geographically definable areas should be possible. In addition, integration into free GIS software is to be made possible so that scientists can carry out further analyses in their own software world.

More at <http://ogham.squared.engineers> link:

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Project page Discussion

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Wikidata:WikiProject OghamStones

- Wikidata Entry: [WikiProject OghamStones](#) (Q129491028) supported by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network (Q73601970)
- Commons Category: [Category:Ogham stones](#)

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Statements to model an Ogham Stone in an exhibition [edit]

Property	Example	description
Statements		
instance of (P31)	ogham stone (Q2010147) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q105602843) archaeological artifact (Q220556)	defines it as an Ogham Stone, archaeological artefact and Ogham Stone Semantic Concept
part of (P381)	WikiProject OghamStones (Q129491028) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q105602843)	part of WikiProjects and a semantic concept
image (P18)	divers	Wikimedia Commons image. If multiple add pref. rank (optional)
country (P17)	divers	country, e.g. Republic of Ireland (Q27)
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	divers	county, e.g. County Cork (Q152475)
location (P276)	divers	museum + exhibition, e.g. University College Cork (Q1574155) + UCC Stone Corridor (Q121562049)
coordinate location (P625)	WGS84	using qualifier location (P276) ex situ (Q1383330), sourcing circumstances (P1485) on-site survey (Q120965426), determination method (P456) on-site survey (Q120965426), subject has role (P2868) exhibition (Q454660), stated in (P248) OpenStreetMap (Q268), reference OpenStreetMap
creator (P170)	Ogham Person Concept (Q111087321)	Ogham Person as creator (only needed if non-free artwork image URL (P8000) is used)
collection (P196)	divers	collection, e.g. Stone Corridor University College Cork (Q65379477)
inventory number (P217)	divers	inventory number of the collection, set a pref. rank
location of discovery (P138)	divers	ogham site, e.g. Barrahaunin (Ogham Site) (Q60378412)
external data available at URL (P1325)	LURL	ref. to 3D-model in Sketchfab, using qualifier object has role (P3831) 3D model (Q3859833), publisher (P123), published in (P1433), copyright license (P276), add pref. rank
inscription (P1854)	latin	inscription, e.g. C[AR]RITACC MMAQI MOU CAGG (Latin)
state of conservation (P5815)	divers	status, e.g. partially destroyed (Q62653910) (optional)
non-free artwork image URL (P8000)	divers	external image (optional), using qualifier copyright license (P276), publisher (P123), object has role (P3831)
partially coincident with (P1382)	divers	other concepts, e.g. BARHA1 (Ogham Stone Concept by CISP) (Q109675166), CIIC 103 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) (Q6037856)
Identifiers		
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11563)	divers	Open Street Map Node

DAS WIKIDATA WIKI PROJECT OGHAM STONES

SFM-KAMPAGNE MIT DER KIRI ENGINE APP

F. Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

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UCC STONE #1 / CIIC 103 IN KIRI ENGINE

F. Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Cork: Ogham Stone CIIC 89/ UCC 7

3D Model

FOLLOWING

Download 3D Model + Add To </> Embed ↗ Share

Triangles: 1.6M ✓ Vertices: 812.8k [More model information](#)

Ogham stone with no. 7 in the UCC collection, exhibited in the Stone Corridor at University College Cork.

Wikidata: [Q70885690](#)

SMR no.: CO074-164—

Made in KiriEngine from 82 photos.

OGHAM STEINE IN MESHLAB UND SKETCHFAB

CIIC 81

- UCC CORK STONE CORRIDOR: #4
- OSM: NODE/11071361392
- WIKIDATA: Q106680733

↑ Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthierygeo

Änderungssatz #139090380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]JSSITT[A]O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

↑ Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 81/ UCC 4

3D Model

b-unicycling
FOLLOWING

📄 1 🗨️ 5 🌟 0

IN COLLECTIONS

 Ogham stones
b-unicycling
📄 13 🗨️ 0 🌟 0

SUGGESTED 3D MODELS

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 128/ UCC 25
b-unicycling
📄 5 🗨️ 0 🌟 1

 Cork: Ogham stone UCC 12/ CIIC 262
b-unicycling
📄 6 🗨️ 0 🌟 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 127/ UCC 20
b-unicycling
📄 6 🗨️ 0 🌟 0

 Cork: Ogham Stone CIIC 89/ UCC 7
b-unicycling
📄 12 🗨️ 0 🌟 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 93/ UCC 8
b-unicycling
📄 10 🗨️ 0 🌟 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 61/ UCC 24
b-unicycling
📄 3 🗨️ 0 🌟 0

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UCC OGHAM STONE #4 IN SKETCHFAB

UCC OGHAM STONE #4 IN 3DHOP VIA *ARCHAEOSQUIRRELS.CLOUD*

Location and history:

According to [Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869](#), 260, the stone was found in a structure called *Rath Lisheenagreine*, in the townland of Gurranes (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mle. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurranes" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map of the rath (in connection with the larger *Rath Lisnacaheragh*) is available in S.P. [O' Rŷordáin's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42](#), 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of [his article in JRSAI 10, 1869](#)); Macalister states in [CIIC](#) that it "has been known since the sixities" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurranes. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches": [CIIC 1, 84](#)). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.

BESCHREIBUNG IN DER TITUS-DATENBANK

H. "Lasheennagreine" Small fort, remains shown here are semi-circular but not marked in 1842. The portion here marked has since been cleared away, as has the fence shown across it. A hollow in the field may be seen and evidently marks the site. An ogham stone was found here and is now in University College, Cork. (*J.C.H.A.S.*, XXVI (1931), 67).

BESCHREIBUNG IN RÍORDÁIN & RYAN (1941/42), PP.78 FF.

C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLPTI

BARONY OF KINALMEAKY

81.—Garranes (84).

1869 JRSAI 10 : 260 (Brash). 1911 * *Ivernian* 3 : 73 (Henebry).

On this townland there is an interesting group of earthworks which have recently been examined by excavation. The

present stone, which has been known since the sixties, appears to have come from a souterrain in the group; in Windele's time it was standing loosely in the ground beside one or two others, but it must have fallen shortly after that; for long it lay prostrate in one of the ditches, where I first saw it. It is now in the Museum of University College, Cork. An irregular pillar

BESCHREIBUNG IN MACALISTER (1945), PP. 83/84

via <https://www.istor.org/stable/25505959>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL; <https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/6168494>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL;
<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/562702954>

alt_name	Garranes Ringfort
archaeological_site	fortification
fortification_type	ringfort
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	celtic
name	Lisnacaheragh Ringfort

RATH CALLED
LISHEENAGREINE
CA. 51.81655, -8.76587

Florian Thiery,
CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

CIIC 81 AT THE ORIGINAL? FINDSPOT IN GARRANES (LISHEENAGREINE)

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

LOOKING AT THE UCC STONE CORRIDOR

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680733)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	Q106680733 ogham stone edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
Q106680733 Ogham Stone Concept	edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
Q106680733 Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
	+ add value

via <https://www.istor.org/stable/25505959>

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

- determination method [georeferencing](#)
- object has role [book entry \(Ogham\)](#)
- subject has role [archaeological site](#)
- statement in [academic journal article](#)

[1 reference](#)

- reference URL <https://www.corkhist.ie/wp-content/uploads/jfiles/1931/b1931-020.pdf>
- <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25505959>

EXAMPLE: CIIC 81 → FOUND IN GARRANES (LISHEENAGREINE)

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680733)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

[In more languages](#)
[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	<div>Q106680733 ogham stone edit</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div>
	<div>Q106680733 Ogham Stone Concept edit</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div>
	<div>Q106680733 Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project) edit</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div> <div>+ add value</div>

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

51°53'37.7254"N, 8°29'31.6313"W

location	ex situ
sourcing circumstances	on-site survey
determination method	on-site survey
subject has role	exhibition
stated in	OpenStreetMap

[▼ 1 reference](#)

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392

EXAMPLE: CIIC 81 → CURRENTLY AT UCC CORK #4

OGHAM STONE GEARS/1 IM CORK PUBLIC MUSEUM

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=CHUIS_1

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=GEARS_1

OGHAM STONES GEARS/1 UND CHUIS/1 IN 3DHOP VIA *ARCHAEOQUIRRELS.CLOUD*

REAL WORLD USE CASES

HOLY WELLS IM COUNTY KILKENNY (IRLAND)

Anne-Karoline

<https://www.youtube.com/@OSM4HistoryBufs>
<https://www.openstreetmap.org/user/b-unicycling/diary>

Distel

OSM FOR HISTORY BUFFS

exploring irish history

Anne-Karoline Distel

@OSM4HistoryBuffs · 872 Abonnenten · 244 Videos

Das Hauptaugenmerk dieses Kanals sind Tutorials zum Kartografieren historischer Stätten.

[facebook.com/OSMForHistoryBuffs](https://www.facebook.com/OSMForHistoryBuffs)

Abonniert

<https://www.youtube.com/@OSM4HistoryBuffs/videos>

<https://youtu.be/VplrkIcq9EA?si=C6YAgdyUnzLEPvEX>

WIKIPROJECT HOLY WELLS - CHECK IT OUT!

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Wikidata:WikiProject HolyWells

Wikidata Entry: [WikiProject HolyWells](#) (Q125443454) supported by the [Research Squirrel Engineers Network](#) (Q73901970)

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 - 1.4 SPARQL List as Map / Image Map
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Holy Wells in Ireland [edit]

Statements to model a holy well in Ireland [edit]

Use English and Irish labels in the header, where known.

Property	Example	Explanation
instance of (P31)	Holy Well Semantic Concept (Q125443332)	always use this: defines it as a holy well, no matter whether there is still veneration happening or not.
	holy well (Q1371047)	
instance of (P31)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • state of use (P5617): "in use" for holy wells where veneration is still happening or "abandoned", where that is the case • state of conservation (P5816): preserved (Q25557591)/ in danger (Q25555026)/ demolished or destroyed (Q25555015) 	
instance of (P31)	religious site (Q10589886)	only where veneration is still happening, i.e. annual patterns or people regularly visiting the well for private prayers or to retrieve the holy water
instance of (P31)	water source (Q10713454)	only where there is actually still water at the site, helps to filter out dried up wells/ springs
country (P17)	Republic of Ireland (Q27)	---
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	County Kilkenny (Q180231) + Balleen (Q50553357)	County + civil parish
diocese (P708)	Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory (Q873907)	Roman Catholic diocese in which the holy well is located
coordinate location (P825)		coordinate location derived from OpenStreetMap or Historic Environment Viewer add reference URL (P254) or stated in (P248)
street address (P3875)		use, when the only location given is a field name or similar
described by source (P1343)	O'Kelly: The Place-Names of County Kilkenny (Q12837401) Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland) (Q120498144) The Schoofs' Collection (Q126303246) Canon W. Carrigan: The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory (Q125454042) with its volumes	add page(s) (P304) or reference URL (P564)
image (P18)		image
video (P15)		
Commons category (P373)	Category:Toberbride, Callan [?]	
named after (P116)	Bright of Kildare (Q88076) eye (Q7354)	saint representing patron saint or body part representing cure for ailment
open days (P3025)		pattern day(s), if it is still celebrated
Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID (P4057)	KK008-133---	plus reference URL (P564)
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11903)	6153432366	OpenStreetMap Node ID or way ID
Wiki Loves Monuments ID (P2186)	IE-KK-0327	WikiLovesMonuments ID (optional for accessible ones)

DAS WIKIDATA WIKI PROJECT HOLY WELLS

Use English and Irish labels in the header, where known.

Property	Example	Explanation
instance of (P31)	Holy Well Semantic Concept (Q126443332)	always use this: defines it as a holy well, no matter whether there is still veneration happening or not.
instance of (P31)	<p>holy well (Q1371047)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> state of use (P5817) "in use" for holy wells where veneration is still happening or "abandoned", where that is the case state of conservation (P5816): preserved (Q56557591)/ in danger (Q55555088)/ demolished or destroyed (Q56556915) 	
instance of (P31)	religious site (Q105889895)	only where veneration is still happening, i.e. annual patterns or people regularly visiting the well for private prayers or to retrieve the holy water
instance of (P31)	water source (Q10713454)	only where there is actually still water at the site, helps to filter out dried up wells/ springs
country (P17)	Republic of Ireland (Q27)	---
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	County Kilkenny (Q180231) + Balleen (Q60553357)	County + civil parish
diocese (P708)	Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory (Q873607)	Roman Catholic diocese in which the holy well is located
coordinate location (P625)		coordinate location derived from OpenStreetMap or Historic Environment Viewer add reference URL (P854) or stated in (P248)
street address (P6375)		use, when the only location given is a field name or similar
described by source (P1343)	<p>O'Kelly; The Place-Names of County Kilkenny (Q126374601)</p> <p>Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland) (Q120966194)</p> <p>The Schools' Collection (Q126393245)</p> <p>Canon W. Carrigan; The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory (Q126454942) with its volumes</p>	add page(s) (P304) or reference URL (P854)
image (P18)		image
video (P10)		
Commons category (P373)	Category:Toberbride, Callan 	
named after (P138)	<p>Brigit of Kildare (Q80979)</p> <p>eye (Q7364)</p>	<p>saint representing patron saint or</p> <p>body part representing cure for ailment</p>
open days (P3025)		pattern day(s), if it is still celebrated
Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID (P4057)	KK006-133----	plus reference URL (P854)
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11693)	6153432366	OpenStreetMap Node ID or way ID
Wiki Loves Monuments ID (P2186)	IE-KK-0327	WikiLovesMonuments ID (optional for accessible ones)

HOLY WELL MODELLIERUNG IN WIKIDATA

Table ⌵ ⓘ 218 Ergebnisse in 39 ms ↔ Code Herunterladen Link

Search 🔍

item	itemLabel	img	geo	osm
Q126454405	St. Finan's Well	commons:Area of St. Finan's Well.jpg	Point(-7.3331526 52.8193781)	11123986964
Q126436485	Saint Brigid's Well		Point(-7.3632748 52.7903396)	11124027029
Q126473043	Tobernadaun		Point(-7.435736 52.619854)	6545440502
Q126388499	Our Lady's Well		Point(-7.3237367 52.869687)	10579420075
Q126476510	Mary's Well		Point(-7.251557 52.651964)	
Q121842432	Saint Flachra's Well	commons:St Flachra's Well Sheastown.jpg	Point(-7.1978959 52.6216672)	8515265450
Q126456487	Well of the Festival	commons:Well of the Festival.jpg	Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237
Q126456487	Well of the Festival	commons:Well of the Festival 2.jpg	Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237
Q126455695	Tobermurry		Point(-7.0412334 52.3693873)	8512077750
Q122302328	Tober Muire		Point(-7.3914627 52.373694)	11134643496
Q126454444	Well of the Rags		Point(-7.3356296 52.5417788)	6557864663
Q114439798	Kenny's Well	commons:Kenny's Well 3.png	Point(-7.26219 52.65325)	1158290017
Q122306366	Lady's Well		Point(-7.4339556 52.6892494)	8515624782
Q126472997	Tobernakill		Point(-7.2451643 52.2695346)	8526290294
Q126456660	Toberatoo		Point(-7.1011717 52.5672147)	8235318731
Q126454380	Little Church Well		Point(-7.384327 52.501843)	
Q122258994	Saint Scoheen's Well	commons:Saint Scoheen's Well Freneystown.jpg	Point(-7.1177989 52.6823464)	7117539440
Q122304309	Saint Molin's Well	commons:St Molin's Well, Mullennakill, Co.Kilkenny - geograph.org.uk - 213492.jpg	Point(-7.11584 52.4307541)	8526433151
Q122307282	Angel's Well	commons:Angel's Well near the Black Abbey.jpg	Point(-7.2569636 52.6542782)	5343898433
Q126456561	St. John's Well		Point(-7.1986981 52.5398448)	6535302216
Q126454436	Q126454436		Point(-7.02032 52.411498)	
Q122114442	Church Well	commons:Church Well, Chatsworth.jpg	Point(-7.1820207 52.8730601)	11123956952
Q122306022	Tobermotua		Point(-7.41438 52.5837967)	11124626340
Q126456648	Tobernagolomb		Point(-7.0324988 52.3277874)	8512066590

HOLY WELLS IN WIKIDATA VIA [HTTPS://W.WIKI/AQ2F](https://w.wiki/AQ2F) (03.09.2024)

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item	itemLabel	img	geo	osm	ed
Q:Q121842432	Saint Fiachra's Well	commons:St Fiachra's Well Sheastown.jpg	Point(-7.1978959 52.6216672)	8515265450	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/sheastown-st-fiachres-well-low-poly-be3bcad3a32047443a3b2255465028b8 >
Q:Q122304309	Saint Molin's Well	commons:St Molin's Well, Mullinakill, Co.Kilkenny - geograph.org.uk - 213492.jpg	Point(-7.11584 52.4307541)	8526433151	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-molings-well-low-poly-dcfaff49b2f34d34d845cade4f889ad33 >
Q:Q126649228	Lacken Well	commons:Lacken Well 1 - Kells, County Kilkenny - geograph.org.uk - 5259695.jpg	Point(-7.2775479 52.5438145)	9886802295	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/garrynamann-lower-lacken-well-d5beb9cc7adb4b248c1bb6c2ec542582 >
Q:Q126487120	St Coleman's Well	commons:St Colman's Well.jpg	Point(-7.2869104 52.7352502)	998532219	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/jenkinstown-st-colmans-well-low-poly-6ae5988530c648aea73cfc09663954a0 >
Q:Q122258894	Saint Fiacre's Well	commons:St Fiachre's Well, Ullard.jpg	Point(-6.9330041 52.5808599)	8512180854	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ullard-st-fiachras-well-low-poly-635f79e64b434a6ea08a76229bf493d >
Q:Q126456441	Columbkille's Well	commons:Inistioge Saint Columbkille's Well.png	Point(-7.0681791 52.4892388)	8513597500	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/inistioge-st-columbkills-well-low-poly-b0845424e49d40c4fa04f376c98ac7f5 >
Q:Q126454844	Lady's Well	commons:Lady's Well in Graiguenamanagh 4.jpg	Point(-6.9566958 52.5411618)	8513574146	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/grauguenamanagh-ladys-well-9ed7bfc22e184897a5b8e758ceff7249e >
Q:Q114439798	Kenny's Well	commons:Kenny's Well 3.png	Point(-7.26219 52.65325)	1158290017	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kennys-well-indoors-low-poly-685c7b9d3b0e4ba09e222633342cfc3 >
Q:Q126456487	Well of the Festival	commons:Well of the Festival.jpg	Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee333390870b4d9888a0bb342029df69 >
Q:Q126456487	Well of the Festival	commons:Well of the Festival 2.jpg	Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee333390870b4d9888a0bb342029df69 >
Q:Q129263926	Holy Well	commons:Saint Nicholas' Well in Newtown Jerpoint.jpg	Point(-7.1637296 52.5134682)	7673751375	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/newtown-erpoint-st-nicholas-well-62521654a1ec4c0ca7430ccbfb448869 >
Q:Q126374490	Trinity Well	commons:Trinity Well at Ballyraffon.jpg	Point(-7.2710769 52.7262158)	11942593399	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ballyraffon-trinity-well-553073f9100040e789890d3edd3dc851 >
Q:Q126458702	St. Nicholas's Well	commons:St Nicholas's Well, Killamery.jpg	Point(-7.4459883 52.4752746)	6167966637	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/killamery-st-nicholas-well-low-poly-0eeb400854164819afc5bae588df8da >
Q:Q122258906	Lady's Well	commons:Lady's Well in its fenced off enclosure.jpg	Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18 >
Q:Q122258906	Lady's Well	commons:Lady's Well.jpg	Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18 >
Q:Q122258906	Lady's Well	commons:Lady's Well with hawthorn tree.jpg	Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18 >
Q:Q122189562	Saint Augustine's Well	commons:County Kilkenny - Saint Augustine's Well - 20230902133128.jpg	Point(-7.38765 52.54522)		< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/callan-st-augustines-well-low-poly-9feacac0fda14a189a1a59d2e129b1e4 >
Q:Q126657210	St. David's Well	commons:Saint David's Well.jpg	Point(-7.2979334 52.6195581)	12144379129	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/castleinch-st-davids-well-4b6eae78a6cc43c2ae79bb6ab7c69a8 >
Q:Q126918993	Kilkeasy Holy Well	commons:Kilkeasy Holy Well.jpg	Point(-7.2246427 52.4410735)	12015630647	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilkeasy-holy-well-67a39daeb3c54539a8ab314ec2b9f367 >
Q:Q121840779	Toberlachtain	commons:Toberlachtain Tober Lachtain 02.jpg	Point(-7.38951 52.7316)	935503837	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/freshford-st-lachtains-well-low-poly-ae1ef14daa7d433dbbf076407134e81e >
Q:Q126454422	St Leonard's Well	commons:St Leonard's Well, Dunnamaggan - geograph.org.uk - 4277319.jpg	Point(-7.2955635 52.5006254)	7412516778	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-leonards-well-c6e89f2e2ae147ba90553a3a16fda690 >

HOLY WELLS MIT SKETCHFAB LINKS ZU 3D-MODELLEN (03.09.2024)

FRESHFORD: ST LACHTAIN'S WELL

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779>

Wikidata

Toberlachtain (Q121840779)

Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny

Total Lachtain (St. Lachtain's Well) - Toberlachtain

+ 12 more languages

Language	Label	Description	Short name
English	Toberlachtain	Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
Arabic	No label defined	No description defined	
Arabic	No label defined	No description defined	

All external languages

Statements

instance of

- holy well
- Holy Well Semantic Concept
- spring

holy well

area of use: abandoned
year to line: 1855

Image

File:Toberlachtain Holy Well (1).jpg
3,000 × 2,000 (5.54 MB)

named after

- Lachtain mac Tairn

country

- Ireland

located in the administrative territorial entity

- County Kilkenny
- Freshford

disease

- Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory

coordinate location

collection

- Patrick O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kilkenny II

inventory number

- 137

medical condition treated

- conjunctivitis
- eye infection

external data available at URL

- https://www70760.com/55-moodyfreshford-st-lachtain-well-2019-06-16/176124742330770427704870/

described by source

- Clifty: The Place-Names of County Kilkenny
- Historic Environment Viewer (Openair)
- The Schoolyard Collection
- Letters containing information relative to the antiquities of the County of Kilkenny considered during the progress of the Ordnance Survey in 1838
- The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory II

described by source

- 6 Inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland
- Patrick O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kilkenny in terms of documentary coverage, location, ritual practice and oronomastic context, vol. I
- Patrick O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kilkenny II
- Notes and Comments of County Kilkenny by Paris Anderson
- Blanchard Cartesell, Theopneustics
- Historical, Social and Political Sketches of Freshford
- Red Book of Ossory

Commons category

- Toberlachtain

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

- KK013-025----

OpenStreetMap node ID

- 50503837

Wiki Loves Monuments ID

- IR-KK-0248

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

KK013-025----

1 reference

OpenStreetMap way ID

935503837

0 references

FRESHFORD: ST LACHTAIN'S WELL IN WIKIDATA

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/935503837>

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen

Weg: Saint Lachtain's Well (935503837)

Version #7
added sketchfab link

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von b-unicycling
Änderungssatz #152597977

Tags

alt_name	Toberlachtain
amenity	place_of_worship
check_date	2023-08-25
denomination	roman_catholic
description	Walled enclosure with wrought iron gate. Stone paved ground with subcircular water basin which is covered in water lentils.
name	Toberlachtain
name:en	Saint Lachtain's Well
name:etymology:wiki	Q18674069
name:ga	Tobar Lachtain
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:ESmr	KK013-025
religion	christian
source	British War Office mapsurvey

FRESHFORD: ST LACHTAIN'S WELL IN OSM

KILLAMERY: ST NICHOLAS'S WELL

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/6167966637>

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen Wo ist dies?

Knoten: Saint Nicholas's Well (6167966637)

Version #13

added wikidata to #holy well

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von b-unicycling
Änderungssatz #152518873
Standort: 52.4752746, -7.4459883

Tags

denomination	roman_catholic
description	Stone lined water basin of c.1m width with a large carved stone marking the spot. Water is covered in water lentils.
drinking_water	no
man_made	water_well
mapillary	759508952563297
name	Saint Nicholas's Well
name:en	Saint Nicholas's Well
name:etymology:wiki data	Q44269
name:ga	Tobar San Niclais
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
pump	no
ref:ESmr	KK030-008007
religion	christian
	O'Kelly: Placenames.

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KILLAMERY: ST NICHOLAS'S WELL IN OSM

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/p7LYv>

Humphrey Bolton, CC BY-SA 2.0, via Wikimedia Commons

MULLENNAKILL: ST MOLING'S WELL

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/8526433151>

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen

Knoten: St. Molin's Well (8526433151)

Version #9

added details to holy well site

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von b-unicycling
Änderungssatz #155288577
Standort: 52.4306885, -7.1158747

Tags

alt_name	Saint Molin's Well
drinking_water	yes
name	St. Molin's Well
name:etymology:wiki	Q4300418
name:ga	Tobar Mholainn
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:esmr	KK036-012001
service_times	20 August
source	British war Office map:survey
subject:wikidata	Q4300418
url:sketchfab	https://skfb.ly/p7LYv
wikidata	Q122304309
wikimedia_commons	File:St Molin's Well, Mullennakill, Co.Kilkenny - geograph.org.uk - 213492.jpg

Teil von

▼ 1 Weg

© OpenStreetMap Mitwirkende Spenden Website und API-Bedingungen

MULLENNAKILL: ST MOLING'S WELL IN OSM

REAL WORLD USE CASES

STEPPING BY ...

ADLERSTEIN IN AACHEN

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Open Street Map Mitwirkende, ODbL

AUF DEM WEG VORBEI IN AACHEN AM DREILÄNDERPUNKT ...

“138 Adlersteine markierten als mittelalterliche Grenzsteine einst die Grenzen des Aachener Reiches. Von denen sind maximal noch 18 Steine zu finden, manche demoliert und unleserlich.”
Quelle: Wikimedia Commons (<https://w.wiki/AmoM>)

... ENTDECKT MAN DEN ADLERSTEIN

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/1128569466>

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen Wo ist das?

Knoten: Adlerstein (1128569466)

Version #8
change image

Bearbeitet vor etwa einem Monat von fthiergeo
Änderungssatz #154519289
Standort: 50.7617299, 6.0187331

Tags

description	No. 16 am Schorenkopf
historic	boundary_stone
image	File:Adlerstein_Aachen_Vaals.jpg
name	Adlerstein
urtsketchfab	https://skfb.ly/p6nO9
website	https://grenzsteine.de/530599968a1463356/0342949925132eF01/index.html
wikimedia_commons	Category:Grenzstein achter Wilhelminatoren, Vaals

XML herunterladen

« Version #1 - Verlauf anzeigen - Version #8 »

© OpenStreetMap Mitwirkende Spenden, Website und API-Bedingungen

ADLERSTEIN IN VAALS (NIEDERLANDE) IN OSM

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/p6n09>

via <http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=NLRMR-36638>

ADLERSTEIN IN VAALS (NIEDERLANDE) IN SKETCHFAB / 3DHOP

REAL WORLD USE CASES

OBJEKTE ALS

INFORMATIONSTRÄGER (IN ROM)

Bilder: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Persisting
with
change

KOLOSSALSTATUE KONSTANTINS DES GROßEN

3D-MODELLE ZUM "PUZZELN"

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_HandKonstantin

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_KopfKonstantin

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_FussKonstantin

3D-MODELLE IN 3DHOP

© Irene Gaumé for Factum Foundation

© Otto Lowe | Factum Foundation

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

3D MODELLE ZUM "PUZZELN"

FIGUR IN DEN DIOKLETIANSTHERMEN: *GANYMED & ZEUS (ADLER)*

FIGUR IN DEN DIOKLETIANSTHERMEN

Daria Stefan, CC BY 4.0

FIGUR IN DEN DIOKLETIANSTHERMEN: *DIONYSOS YOUNG & OLD*

Bilder: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Book of Jonah (Old Testament)

The word of the Lord came to Jonah, "Go to the great city of Nineveh and preach against it, because its wickedness has come up before me."

Triumph of Neptune and the Four Seasons, 2nd-4th century

via <https://youtu.be/x4WzBbdG9IU?si=d2pGkWRsD0vvtok&t=46>

via https://youtu.be/x4WzBbdG9IU?si=Qc0KPBLWtSGZ_iCU&t=77

SANTA MARIA ANTIQUA SARCOPHAGUS

SANTA MARIA ANTIQUA SARCOPHAGUS

BILDERWELTEN IN DEN DIOKLETIANSTHERMEN AUF EINEM SARKOPHAG

INSCRIFT IN DEN DIOKLETIANSTHERMEN VON *MARCUS CLAUDIUS*

INSCRIFT IN DEN DIOKLETIANSTHERMEN VON *MILITÄRDIPLOMEN*

BILDERWELTEN IN DEN DIOKLETIANSTHERMEN AUF EINEM SARKOPHAG

CONCLUSIO

Fotos:
Florian Thiery,
CC BY 4.0

(3D-)DIGITALISIERT UND MAPPED FLEIßIG IN OSM UND WIKIDATA

FINIS!

QUESTIONS?

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Macalister, Robert Alexander Stewart. *Corpus Inscriptionum Insularum Celticarum*. Vol. I. Dublin: Stationery Office, 1945.